

**THE IMPORTANCE OF MONETARY POLICY IN ENSURING THE
STABILITY OF PUBLIC FINANCE**

Tursunmurodov Sirojiddin

Master of the Academy of Banking

Finance of the Republic of Uzbekistan

Today, a period of economic transition has revealed evidence of the role played by financial and foreign exchange instruments in the growth of the economy, considerably altering public perceptions of their significance and order of importance in the system of state regulation of a growing market economy. Raising monetary policy is therefore appropriate to ensure the stability of public finances.

Before beginning a discussion on the work in this regard, it is acceptable to quote various theories to gain a better understanding of public finance and monetary policy:

The organization, allocation, and use of the financial resources at the disposal of the government constitute the single field of public finance.

Public finance resources are initially channeled toward advancing national objectives. Public finance also provides a service in carrying out governmental duties.

Money resources, financial mechanisms, state financial institutions (offices), and financial policy are all components of public finance. By this point, the role of public finance in carrying out the state's financial and economic policy has grown even more.

It has established itself as a key tool for controlling the state as well as for insuring the processes of reproduction, creating the conditions for people to live rich lives on both a material and spiritual level, and making up for the ample supply of state institutions. We also have what is considered to be monetary policy.

The central bank can directly affect the money market while implementing a monetary policy by using its management authority and by emitting money.

monetary policy is implemented both directly and indirectly: 1) Direct means—prices of financial assets in financial institutions expressed as percentage rates, or direct control over the size of the institutions.

The bank's current deposit in commercial banks serves as central money, which also controls the prices and volume of loans that are granted. 2) indirect methods—the central bank's use of financial institutions

The money mass in the economy is impacted by resursit market processes (mandated reserve requirements, open market operations, commercial banks refinancing, the central bank's account rate, deposits from commercial banks through acceptance, etc.). The concept of development and implementation of monetary policy of the Central Bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the medium term was developed taking into account the leading role of the communications channel in the formation of public opinion and the implementation of the inflation-targeting regime in practice. The purpose of this concept is to convey to the general public the conceptual framework for the transition to inflationary targeting, as well as the medium-term plans to create the necessary conditions for the successful implementation of this monetary policy regime in practice and explain in detail.

The role of monetary policy in ensuring macroeconomic stability and development

Ensuring domestic price stability in the country is a guarantee of macroeconomic and social stability and is a necessary condition for the successful implementation of programs for accelerating and developing economic reforms.

In this case, low and stable indicators of inflation are considered an important factor in ensuring balanced economic growth, increasing production competitiveness and living standards of the population. In this context, the decline

and stabilization of price growth rates should be one of the main goals of State Economic Policy.

Transmission (transfer) mechanism of monetary policy

In ensuring price stability in the economy, the existence of a mechanism of effective impact of monetary policy measures on the level of gross demand and inflation is of critical importance.

In inflationary targeting mode, the central bank changes and sets interest rates based on the target set by inflation. When inflationary risks increase in the economy, the Central bank traditionally tightens money-credit by raising interest rates. The degree and duration of influence of these measures on the real sector of the economy is determined by the effectiveness of monetary policy transmission mechanisms.

The transmission mechanism of monetary policy in itself reflects the process by which the central bank affects the economic activity and, ultimately, the level of inflation of changes in interest rates.

It is unquestionably required to use a variety of techniques in order to produce just a high outcome in the future in order to successfully implement monetary policy. To illustrate this, it is appropriate to list the current, well-known approaches of monetary policy that are relevant to mention:

- open market transactions (promissory notes, government bonds, and other valuable buying and selling papers);
- regulation of economic standards for banks (cash reserves and deposits, own the relationship between capital and loan capital and assets, etc.);
- direct limitation of the amount of certain types of loans that may be made; change in the standards for mandatory reserves of banks; and open market transactions.

REFERENCES:

1. <https://www.ebsco.com>
2. https://uz.wikipedia.org/wiki/Davlat_moliyasi/
3. https://uz.wikipedia.org/wiki/Pul-kredit_siyosati/
4. <https://cbu.uz/uz/monetary-policy/concept/>

